

Proposed Business Model Using Business Model Canvas (BMC) to Increase Neutrafix Platform Users (Case Study: PT Telekomunikasi Indonesia International)

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ABSTRACT: This comprehensive study, entitled “Propose Business Model using Business Model Canvas to Increase Neutrafix Platform User”, Neutrafix is a voice & mobility e-commerce platform owned by PT Telekomunikasi Indonesia International (Telin). Through comprehensive analyses, including Business Model Canvas, VRIO, PESTEL, Porter's Five Forces, and STP, key challenges and opportunities were identified. This study aim to fix the challenge that Neutrafix currently facing like stagnan growth, a prepaid payment model unfavorable to buyers, and the absence of large sellers, which in the end resulted in low platform user. This study utilize a qualitative approach, using a semi structured interview and a thorough of secondary data. This methodology enables a comprehensive examination of current internal and external situation of Neutrafix. The study focus on Neutrafix business issue and how to improve it. The main conclusions emphasized problems including misalignment of value proposition, Ineffective communication, Lack of customer support, and opportunities for strategic partnership. In response, this thesis recommends three strategic actions: forming a strategic partnership with Etisalat, introducing flexible payment options as a new value proposition, and establishing a Customer Success team to manage customer relationships that translated into customer satisfaction and user increase.

KEYWORD: Business Model Canvas, Platform User, Strategic Partnership, Value Proposition.

INTRODUCTION

With the development of digital technology that is increasingly significant throughout the world, the era of Indonesia 4.0 is getting closer. Through increasing productivity that affects every lifeline, digitalization has an extreme impact on entering the joints of the lives of all people of the world in all sectors. With digitization, there is a simplification of every activity in life with the use of the internet. In today's era, the internet plays an important role in human daily activities, both in terms of access to information and knowledge and the role of the internet in supporting individuals and organizations in carrying out daily tasks, business operations, communication, and collaboration. Not only in daily activities that involve people who are around, but the internet has a positive impact on openness in the aspect of global accessibility. This can be an opportunity to develop a telecommunications business that combines the public's need for the internet and open public access to exposure to the global world at a wider scale. Neutrafix. a digital public connectivity exchange or marketplace, aims at resolving the connectivity piece of the puzzle where the company lacks. Bringing together carriers, operators and enterprises to Neutrafix is key for PT. Telekomunikasi Indonesia International (Telin) as a Carrier to be successful. This provides the company business missing link, not only we gain the interconnects, we are disrupting the CPaaS and wholesale market by allowing Enterprises the freedom to choose their preferred partner and hopefully PT. Telekomunikasi Indonesia International (Telin) as one of the many carriers vying for business. Neutrafix is currently the only marketplace in the world that transparently connects buyers and sellers. Digital transformation on PT. Telekomunikasi Indonesia International (Telin) legacy business is a must in order to gain that edge in the crowded and fragmented market. Operational efficiency is not optional, and neither can we address it in a piecemeal manner. Neutrafix aims to set a benchmark within TELIN on how digitization of legacy business could improve our efficiency and operational cost. In the same token, Neutrafix aims to position ourselves as our customer's digital transformation partner in the voice, SMS, and numbers legacy business. In developing the Neutrafix, the company has 3 stages which is the development, mass collection, and gaining profit. Currently, Neutrafix is in the second stage, and preparing for the next stage on gaining profit.

BUSINESS ISSUE

During the development of Neutrafix, it was pre-determined that there would be three stages they were developing the app, collecting users, and increasing profit. During the development phase, Telin partnered with Telecoms Xchange (TCXC) a Cloud-based exchange platform for voice, SMS, and numbers with Choose Your Own Carrier (CYOC) technology and programmable API for developers. TCXC helps Telin in developing the application from scratch and also help with the business process inside the application. By the late 2020 Telin and TCXC has successfully completed the development of Neutrafix. In The next stage Telin has shift its focus towards collecting users, this phase is characterized by a dedicated commitment to onboarding a significant user base, with Telin setting a key performance indicator (KPI) of acquiring 300 users in the calendar year 2024. The efforts is done by doing marketing efforts like events and direct marketing. Currently, Neutrafix has around 250+ user in the platform. At the events candidate are offered with express sign which took less time than signing up manually through the web, Neutrafix also explains their main feature on why they should use Neutrafix instead of manual transaction. The result is most of the candidate are agree and decide to join the platform but in the other hand there are only small percent of transaction done by the user, most of the transaction is done by Telin or internal transaction. Currently Neutrafix has over 250 Member with \$133 Million transaction, and more than 1 billion in volume. Based on internal data, most of the transactions are dominated by internal which means PT. Telekomunikasi Indonesia International as the owner of Neutrafix is the seller or the buyer and only 5% of the transactions are organic, from this data, the company has to think about how to increase the organic transaction percentage which later on can be described as increasing revenue or profit. In this case the problem that occurs in Neutrafix as one of Telin's products is low platform users. The author believes that Telin needs a new business strategy to develop the product which is NeutraFix. Given that Neutrafix is a Business-to-Business (B2B) product, the author considers that Neutrafix requires special treatment, especially in developing the strategy of the product. In this case the author considers that Telin needs to make new business formulations in the Neutrafix. The author thinks it needs to be done so that the existence of Neutrafix as a business product can still be sustained and provide profits to the company. The problems faced by Telin in Neutrafix are very regrettable considering that the author feels that this product has good and promising potential for the company. The obstacles of the product, must be addressed immediately so that the existence of Neutrafix can continue to run as a business product. The author considers Both of these things to be the main reason why Neutrafix as a business product still does not benefit the company. So in this research, the author proposes a new business strategy using Business Model Canvas to increase platform users of NeutraFix.

METHODOLGY

In this research the author use qualitative methodology with the aim to understand the current Internal and External conditions of the product Neutrafix, to create a solid business model to increase the Platform Users of Neutrafix, and to have an implementation plan of the proposed Business Strategy to increase Platform Users for Neutrafix in the next 6 months. For this research, data were collected through primary and secondary sources. Primary data were collected through interviews with the management of PT Telekomunikasi Indonesia International and five consumers as a sample, while secondary data were collected through articles, journals, and websites.

RESULT

Internal Analysis

A. Segmenting, Targeting, Positioning (STP)

Through the use of this STP analysis, Neutrafix is able to precisely pinpoint and identify the most lucrative B2B market sectors, guaranteeing customized approaches that address the unique requirements of buyers and sellers in the telecom sector. Neutrafix segments its market based on the size and type of telco companies.

Firmographic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Industry: Technology, Telco ● Company Size: Small, Medium, and Large corporation ● Revenue: Small, Medium, and High revenue companies ● Type: Hyperscaler, Carrier
Geographic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Global, but currently focus in Asia-Pacific
Behavioural	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Wholesale ● Retail
Need based segmentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cost efficiency, ● High Quality ● Speed of delivery

Figure 1. Segmentation

While the target of Neutrafix products is divided into two, namely Buyer and Seller. In this case, it is further explained that the Target Buyer of NeutraFix product is a telecommunication business with a small to large scale that requires a reliable product, high volume voice, and SMS Service and looks for cost efficiency with high-quality service. While the Seller, in this case NeutraFix targets a Big telecommunications company that wants to have fast transactions and a platform with lots of buyers.

1	Buyer	Small to large telco companies needing reliable, high-volume voice and SMS services who looks for cost efficiency and high-quality services.
2	Seller	Big Telco operator/service who wants to have fast transactions and a platform with lot of buyers.

Figure 2. Targeting

And last the product positioning of Neutrafix was created as a service platform for telecommunications companies that is reliable, high-quality, and cost-effective.

Business Model Canvas (BMC)

Neutrafix is a transparent marketplace that generates revenue through subscriptions and transaction fees, providing significant value. Platform technology and qualified labor are essential resources, while platform maintenance, marketing, and customer service are important tasks. Allocating funds and forming strategic alliances are essential for maintaining operations.

Figure 3. Neutrafix BMC

VRIO Framework

In the Valuable Resource aspect, NeutraFix has good value as a product. The only public exchange in the world, NeutraFix transparently connects buyers and sellers using a straightforward Pay As You Go (PAYG) model. NeutraFix, as a business product of Telin is included in rare products. NeutrafiX is the world's only public exchange that transparently links Buyers and Sellers. NeutraFix as a product was costly to imitate. This is reasonable because the cost of product infrastructure is relatively high, on top of the fact that labor and human resources are insufficient to meet industry demand. As a result, NeutraFix remains the only product in Indonesia to date that can offer services to the general public in accordance with customer needs.

	Capability	Valuable?	Rare?	Costly to Imitate?	Well organized	Conclusion
Tangible Resources						
Financial	Able to generate internal funds	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Sustainability Competitive Advantage
Technological	The technology applied in product	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Sustainability Competitive Advantage
Labor	Competent and Experienced Crew for the operation.	Yes	No	Yes	No	Temporary Competitive Advantage
Intangible Resources						
Organizational	Participate in and contribute to professional organizational cultures.	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Temporary Competitive Advantage
Innovation	Capable to innovate new products	Yes	No	Yes	No	Temporary Competitive Advantage
	Able to increase organizational capacities and innovation	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Temporary Competitive Advantage
Reputation	Consistency on marketing and branding	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Temporary Competitive Advantage

Figure 4. VRIO Framework

External Analysis

A. PESTEL Analysis

Neutrafix operates in an industry heavily regulated by telecommunications laws. Neutrafix need to ensure the regulatory compliance, while Neutrafix's growth and revenue are influenced by economic conditions. Economic downturns may lead to reduced telecommunications spending by companies, affecting Neutrafix's bottom line. Neutrafix benefits from reliance on digital communication technologies and e-commerce platforms The growing adoption of mobile communication services creates a favorable market environment for Neutrafix to expand its customer base. Neutrafix has opportunities to leverage rapid advancements in telecommunications technology, to innovate its platform and offer cutting-edge services to customers. In the other hand Neutrafix may face pressure to adopt energy-efficient technologies and sustainable practices in its operations to minimize environmental impact and meet regulatory requirements. Compliance with data protection laws is critical for Neutrafix to protect customer data and avoid legal liabilities. Non-compliance can result in hefty fines and damage to its reputation.

Political	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regulatory Compliance Government Policies 	Threat	Neutrafix operates in an industry heavily regulated by telecommunications laws. Neutrafix need to ensure regulatory compliance
Economic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Economic Conditions Currency Fluctuations 	Threat	Neutrafix's growth and revenue are influenced by economic conditions. Economic downturns may lead to reduced telecommunications spending by companies, affecting Neutrafix's bottom line
Sociological	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Technological Adoption Consumer Behavior 	Opportunities	Neutrafix benefits from reliance on digital communication technologies and e-commerce platforms. The growing adoption of mobile communication services creates a favorable market environment for Neutrafix to expand its customer base.
Technological	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Technological Advancements Cybersecurity Threats 	Opportunities	Neutrafix has opportunities to leverage rapid advancements in telecommunications technology, to innovate its platform and offer cutting-edge services to customers.
Ecological	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy Efficiency Carbon footprint 	Threat	Neutrafix may face pressure to adopt energy-efficient technologies and sustainable practices in its operations to minimize environmental impact and meet regulatory requirements.
Legal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Protection Laws 	Threat	Compliance with data protection laws is critical for Neutrafix to protect customer data and avoid legal liabilities. Non-compliance can result in hefty fines and damage to its reputation.

Figure 5. PESTEL Analysis

B. Porter Five Force

Until now the threat of new entrants of NeutraFix tends to be low. This is reasonable because developing a product like NeutraFix requires a fairly large budget allocation and qualified infrastructure, While the bargaining power of suppliers is high due to the large number of sellers and switching costs to another platform. On the one hand, there are not a few consumers who choose to continue using NeutraFix even though they need to spend a high budget because until now there has been no product that can provide the same service as that offered by NeutraFix. So, with this condition, the author considers that Neutrafix has a bargaining power of buyers that tends to be moderate (medium). According to the interviews with respondents, it was mentioned that until now there is still no other company that has the infrastructure that Telin has.

Therefore, there is no product that can be a substitute for NeutraFix. According to this situations, the author determines that NeutraFix has threats of substitute products of service that tend to be low. According to the interviews with respondents, it is said that there are still consumers who choose to use other platforms instead even though they cannot get the same service as NeutraFix. Thus, the author assesses that NeutraFix has existing rivals that tend to be moderate (medium).

Five Force	Attractive Level			Summary
	Low	Medium	High	
Threat of new entrant	✓			Threat of new entrant are low due to high entry barrier due to high cost on developing a platform.
Bargaining power of Supplier (seller)			✓	The bargaining power of suppliers is high due to: large number of seller, switching cost to another platform.
Bargaining power of Buyer		✓		The bargaining power of buyers is medium due to Neutrafix give access to connect buyer with giant telco seller
Threat of Substitute product or service	✓			The threat of substitutes for Neutrafix's specialized e-commerce platform is low due to its unique value proposition and the substitute for it is only traditional transaction
Rivalry among existing competitor		✓		The rivalry among existing competitor is moderate to high due to currently there is not much voice and sms e commerce platform

Figure 6. Porter Five Force

According to the analysis above, there has several things that the author can summarize related with the root cause of problem from Neutrafix, included misalignment of the value proposition which is the prepaid method offered by Neutrafix, while beneficial for sellers, may be perceived as a disadvantage for buyers. Ineffective communication strategy, although it is target at the right segment, Neutrafix may deliver a wrong value proposition such as the prepaid method where it can be seen as negative value for buyer. Lack of dedicated customer support, it is possible that current customers are not receiving enough support or incentives to keep using the platform on a regular basis, which emphasizes the necessity of having specialized customer success teams to improve user satisfaction and retention. Opportunities for strategic partnerships, Neutrafix may gain from establishing important alliances with major telecom companies, which would increase its credibility and market reach and create room for expansion. Neutrafix can boost user engagement and draw in new customers by broadening its product offerings, which will aid in the company's overall expansion and success.

PROPOSED BUSINESS MODEL BASED ON BMC

Within the telecom sector, Neutrafix functions as an e-commerce platform that makes voice and SMS service transactions easier. To increase the platform user of Neutrafix there are some strategy needs to be implemented.

Strategic Partnership with Etisalat, Neutrafix is aware of the tremendous potential that exists in forming a strategic alliance with Etisalat, one of the top Middle Eastern telecom providers. Through this cooperation, Neutrafix hopes to increase its market share in high-potential areas by utilizing Etisalat's vast network and influence. Neutrafix can promote new business prospects, increase its credibility, and attract new users by utilizing Etisalat's client base and resources.

Flexible Payment Option as the new Value Proposition, Neutrafix needs to redefining its value proposition by offering its users flexible payment choices. Neutrafix strives to provide individualized payment plans since it understands how important it is to

satisfy a range of consumer preferences. This new value proposition not only increases client satisfaction but also reaffirms Neutrafix's dedication to offering services that are convenient, reasonably priced, and flexible. Customer Success as a New Workforce to Handle Customer Relationships, by hiring a committed staff to handle client relations efficiently, Neutrafix is embracing the idea of customer success. The primary responsibilities of this new group of Customer Success Managers will be to drive value realization, actively engage with customers, and make sure their needs are addressed. By placing a high priority on client success and happiness, Neutrafix hopes to deepen user interactions, increase retention rates, and spur long-term growth.

Figure 7. Proposed Business Model based on BMC

IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

Forming each implementation plan it will consist of planning, implementing, and evaluation. The duration of this plan will be set at six month period, for strategic partnership, the planning consists of asses sales traffic, developing a pricing scheme, developing a partnership scheme, and developing the MoU, this phase will be done in the first two months. And for the implementation would be the next four month which consist of MoU signing, onboarding, implementing pricing and advertisement, and data collection, followed by evaluation like transaction monitoring, reporting, and final evaluation meeting.

For flexible payment options, the planning consists of concept-making, meeting with the developer, feature development, and user acceptance test that will be done in the first four month, and in the last two month there will be the live implementation of the features followed by reporting in the last month

For Customer Success as the new workforce the planning would be in the first three month which consist of developing the requirement for the position, selection process, assessment, until negotiation and selection process, after that in the implementing phase there will be probation and onboarding in the next 3 months period, and in the last phase there will be appointment letter for the selected candidate.

CONCLUSION

Neutrafix, an e-commerce platform for voice and SMS services has honed its strategy by using in-depth evaluations such as Porter's Five Forces, STP, BMC, VRIO, SWOT, and PESTEL. These assessments emphasized the significance of political, economic, social, technological, environmental, and legal variables while also identifying important consumer segments, strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. Strategic recommendations include partnering with Etisalat to expand market reach, introducing flexible payment options to enhance customer satisfaction, and establishing a Customer Success team to improve customer relationships and retention. The objective of these initiatives are to make sure long-term growth in the telecom industry, enhance user engagement, and strengthen Neutrafix's position in the market.

REFERENCES

1. Antony, J., Perry, D., Wang, C., & Kumar, M. (2006). An application of Taguchi method of experimental design for new product design and development process. *Assembly Automation*, 26(1), 18-24.
2. Naibaho, L. (2022). *Introduction to Educational Research: Quantitative and Qualitative Research* (G. A. Siregar (ed.)). Widina Bhakti Persada.
3. Thompson, Arthur A., Peteraf, Margaret A., Gamble, John E., Strickland III, A.J., (2020). *Crafting and Executing Strategy: The Quest for competitive advantage – concepts and cases*, 22th Ed. (22). New York: Mcgraw-Hill Education.
4. Jabareen, Y. (2009). Building a Conceptual Framework: Philosophy, Deginitions, and Procedure. *International Journal of Qualitative Methodology*, 49–62.
5. Kotler, P., & Keller, K. . (2016). *Marketing Management, Global Edition* (Global Edi). Pearson Limited Education.
6. Kotler, P., & Armstrong, G. (2018). *Principles of Marketing* (17th Globa). Pearson Limited Education.
7. Rothaermal, F. (2021). *Strategic Management* (5th ed.). McGraw-Hill Education.
8. Arafat, L. (2018). Faktor Eksternal Industri Pariwisata di Kota Padang dengan Pendekatan PESTEL Analisis. *Jurnal Pariwisata Pesona*, 145–157.
9. Barney, J. B., & Hesterly, W. S. (2020). *Strategic Management and Competitive Advantage* (6th ed.). Pearson Limited Education.
10. Widjaya, P. G. (2018). Analisis Segmenting, targeting, Positioning dan Marketing Mix. *Journal of Economic, Business and Accounting (COSTING)*, 5.
11. Juliandi, F., Niati, A., & Rizkiana, Ci. (2021). Strategi Bauran Pemasaran untuk Meningkatkan Volume Penjualan. *SOLUSI: Jurnal Ilmiah Bidang Ilmu Ekonomi*, 19, 181–190.
12. Benyamin, A. (2019). Strategi Bauran Pemasaran (Marketing Mix Strategy) di Pasarkita Pamulang. *Jurnal Pemasaran Kompetitif*, 1–9.
13. Dilshad, S., Ramachandran, M., & Hoseinian, A. (2017). Disaster Management System as an Element of Risk Management for Natural Disaster Systems Using the PESTLE Framework. *The Security Challenges of the Connected World*, 1–12.
14. Karmila, P. S., Gusti, A. N., Suci, I., & Pratama, M. (2021). Sustainability of the climate village program to prevent the impact of climate change on water supply and sanitation: a perspective from the PESTLE analysis. *2nd International Conference and Disaster and Management*, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/708/1/012086>
15. Kabir, M. S. S. (2016). *Basic Guidleine for Research: An Introductory Approach for All Disciplines. (1st Digital ed.)*. Book Zone Publication
16. Cresswell, J.W. (2014). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches. (4th ed.)*. USA: Library of Congress Cataloging in Publication Data.

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